

**THE EFFECT OF RECRUITMENT, TRAINING
AND PLACEMENT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF
EMPLOYEES IN P.T ASTRA INTERNATIONAL TBK,
TOYOTA AUTO 2000 SM. RAJA MEDAN**

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Abstract:

This study aims to identify and analyze the influence of recruitment, training, and placement on the employees' performance of PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. Data collection in this study was conducted through a survey approach by distributing questionnaires. The population of this research is permanent employees of PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan of as many as 145 people with the number of samples to be studied was 59 people. Methods of data analysis employed descriptive analysis. Data analysis techniques using multiple linear regression analysis aimed to calculate the effect of variables in order to show the influence of recruitment, training, and placement on employee performance. Hypothesis testing used simultaneous test (F-Test) and partial influence test (t-test). Results showed simultaneously that the recruitment, training and placement gave positive and significant impact on employee performance. Partially, variable of recruitment, training, placement have positive and significant influence, with variable of training affects the performance of employees more dominantly at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja of Medan.

Keywords: recruitment, training, placement, employee performance

1. Introduction

Human Resources Management is important element in achieving objectives. In general, the leadership of the company is expecting a good performance from each

employee in the tasks given by the company. The company realizes that human resources are the basic capital in the development process of the company. Therefore, good quality resources will support a quality employee performance and should be developed and directed in order to achieve the goals set by the company.

Some activities in managing human resources include recruitment, training and placement. Recruitment is a practice or activity by the organization with the main purpose to identify and bind to potential employees (Kaswan, 2012: 66). Recruitment is a series of activities aimed to find and attract job applicants with the motivation, abilities, expertise and knowledge needed to cover the shortcomings identified in staff planning. According to Hardjanto (2012: 69-70), training is part of education which is characterized as specific, practical, and immediate.

Specific training means training should be in accordance with those aspects needed by employees. The training followed should also be in a form of practical and easy to understand manual. The techniques taught and introduced should be able to be mastered quickly. This means that knowledge gained can be immediately put into practice in which the employees used to support their performance. Bangun (2012: 159) states that the placement is related to the adjustment of one's abilities and talents to the work that is going to implement. Placing employees in the right position in accordance with the background, ability, experience possessed is one of the tasks of a manager. The ability of managers to place employees based on evaluating performance evaluations objectively will improve organizational achievement and for employees themselves. The work provided and responsibilities in accordance to qualifications are held so that employees produce quality work. The benefit of the placement is to have the function as "*The Right Man on The Right Place*", where it is a guide for managers in placing the workforce in their company.

According to Wibowo (2013: 48) performance is the responsibility of each individual to work, helps to define performance expectations, and seeks a framework for supervisors and workers to communicate with each other. Employee performance needs to be considered because self-confidence and self-esteem of employees are very influential on the results of work. With self-confidence, employees who feel able to complete their tasks will tend to have completed effectively. So that the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him as argued by Mangkunegara (2013: 67).

According to Sutanto and Kurniawan (2016) there is a significant influence between recruitment, employee retention, labor relations on employee performance. Keffi (2017) also argues that recruitment methods have a good influence in screening prospective employees who really excel and influence business performance and progress. In addition, Okechukwu (2017) states that effective employee training and development methods have a positive, efficient and energetic impact on organizational strategies in improving employee performance. Shafiq (2017) states that efficient training has an impact that is, the benefits / advances are enormous for the company and for the employees themselves, making employees who are reliable, knowledgeable,

and build a network of skilled employees. Likewise, Kartika (2014) stated that the recruitment process was good yet the strain faced in the process was that it was difficult to get prospective applicants as needed; the selection process was carried out according to applicable regulations, and placement that had met good categories. Similarly, Al Avisena (2016) said that selection and placement have positive and significant effect on employee performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Recruitment

According to Mardianto (2014: 8) recruitment is defined as a process to get prospective employees who have abilities that are in accordance with the qualifications and needs of an organization. Furthermore, Kaswan (2012: 66) states that recruitment is a practice or activity carried out by an organization with the main objective of identifying and binding potential employees. According to L. Mathis, Robert & H. Jackson, John (2011: 207) recruitment is the process of producing a group of applicants who qualify for work. Based on the opinion above, it can be concluded that recruitment is a process to obtain a number of qualified human resources to occupy a position or job within an organization. Recruitment is an important problem for organizations in terms of procurement of labor. Success in recruitment is largely determined by several indicators that must be carried out during recruitment.

2.2 Training

According to Mangkunegara (2013: 50) training is a short-term educational process that uses systematic and organized procedures, non-managerial employees learn knowledge and technical skills in limited goals. According to Rivai (2010: 212) the principles of training, namely:

- 1) Parties given training (trainees) must be motivated to learn and be trained.
- 2) Trainees must have the ability to learn.
- 3) The training process must be forced or strengthened.
- 4) Training must provide materials that can be practiced or applied.
- 5) The materials presented must have a complete and fulfilling meaning.
- 6) The material taught must have a comprehensive and rewarding meaning.

Jackson (2011: 4) states that "*Companies that have high competitiveness use training practices to improve the ability of workers to implement the company's business strategy*". Based on the opinions above, it can be interpreted that every organization really needs the implementation of training to implement the organization's business strategy in improving the performance of its employees. High employee performance is believed to help the organization to achieve its goals.

2.3 Placement

Employee placement is not advanced from recruitment and training, namely, placing prospective employees who are accepted into positions or jobs that need it and at the same time delegating responsibility. If this function is not implemented properly then it will naturally have a lethal impact on achieving organizational goals. The good workforce who fits a job will affect the amount and quality of workforce (Mathis and Jackson, 2012: 262). According to Siswanto (2012: 164) the work placement procedure is a chronological order to place the right employee in the right position. The procedure of work placement taken is the output of decision making carried out based on rational considerations and based on scientific objective considerations. Flippo (2013: 58) argues that to fulfill placement procedures, personnel must fulfill three preliminary statements:

- 1) There must be authority for personnel assignments that come from personnel request lists that are developed through workplace analysis.
- 2) The person in charge of placement must have a personnel standard that is used to compare prospective workers. This standard is stated by job specifications developed through job analysis.
- 3) Officers must have job applicants to be selected and to be placed.

Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that the placement of employees is an effort to channel the capabilities of employees as well as placing employees in the position or position that is most suitable for obtaining optimal work performance.

2.4 Employee performance

According to Mangkunegara (2013: 67) performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that an employee achieves in carrying out his duties according to the responsibilities given to him. According to Rivai (2010: 42) performance is the work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with the authority and responsibility of each, in order to achieve organizational goals. According to Mangkuprawira (2013: 155) there are several employee performance factors which listed as follows:

- 1) Leadership and trust factors, including elements of knowledge, skills, ability to confidence, motivation and commitment that is owned by each individual employee.
- 2) Manager leadership factors, including aspects of the quality of managers and team leaders in providing encouragement, enthusiasm, direction, and work support to employees.
- 3) Team factors, including the quality of support and enthusiasm given by colleagues in one team, trust in fellow team members, cohesiveness and closeness of team members.
- 4) System factors, including work systems, work facilities or infrastructure provided by the organization.

- 5) Contextual (situational) factors, including pressure and changes in the external and internal environment.

Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that performance is the result of work achievement in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

2.5 Research Methods

This research was conducted on all employees of PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. The study population was 145 permanent employees. The Slovin formula was used to determine the number of samples. Based on calculations using the Slovin formula, the number of samples obtained was as many as 59 employees. The researcher used proportional random sampling for sampling techniques. The data collection technique in this study is to provide a list of statements (questionnaires) to the employees of PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan who has been a research respondent.

The description of the research conceptual framework is as follows:

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

3. Research Results and Discussion

PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 is a company engaged in the network of sales, maintenance, repair and supply of Toyota spare parts that was established in 1975 under the name Astra Motor Sales and only in 1989 changed its name to AUTO 2000 with management that was handled fully by PT. Astra International Tbk. PT. Astra International, Tbk Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan started operations on February 1, 1976 and is located at Jalan Sisingamangaraja No. 8 Medan. This branch is a distributor of Toyota motor vehicles for North Sumatra and Aceh regions. In marketing vehicles, the company has several dealers and sub-dealers located in North Sumatra and Aceh. These dealers help companies market their goods, where all goods marketed are from the head office located in Jakarta. In addition to marketing Toyota brand cars, PT. Astra International, Tbk Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan also sells original spare parts for Toyota brand vehicles. The results of collecting respondents' data based on the gender used as samples that can be seen in Table 1.1 below:

Table 1.1: Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

No.	Gender	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	52	88,14
2.	Female	7	11,86
Total		59	100,00

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed data)

Based on Table 1.1, the results of the research on gender characteristics obtained an illustration that there were 52 male respondents (88.14%) and 7 female respondents (11.86%). This shows that employees who work at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan are predominantly male, as many as 52 people (88.14%). The results of collecting respondents' data based on the age taken as sample can be seen in Table 1.2 below:

Table 1.2: Characteristics of Respondents by Age

No.	Age	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	20 – 29	27	45,76
2.	30 – 39	24	40,68
3.	≥ 40	8	13,56
Total		59	100,00

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed data)

Table 1.2 showed that according to research conducted by age characteristics, that respondents between 20-29 years of age group are as many as 27 people (45.76%) subsequently; respondents between 30-39 years of age group are as many as 24 people (40.68%). On the other hand, there are 8 respondents who aged 40 years and older (13.56%). The data collected from respondents sample on the basis of occupation can be seen in Table 1.3 below:

Table 1.3: Characteristics of Respondents by Job Title

No.	Job Title	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	Customer Relation Department	10	16,9
2.	Administration Department	12	20,3
3.	Sales Department	16	27,1
4.	Service Department	21	35,6
Total		59	100,0

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed data)

Table 1.3 showed respondents based on the characteristics of occupation and displayed that the most dominant job titles of respondent are as employee of Service Department, which has 21 individuals (35.59%). Based on the job title of the respondent above, it has been shown that employees working at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan are employees in the Service Department who are urgently needed to

help handle the repair and maintenance of motor vehicles. They usually are placed both inside and outside the company's workshop. The data collected from the respondents on the basis of work period can be seen in Table 1.4 below.

Table 1.4: Characteristics of Respondents Based Work Period

No.	Work Period (Year)	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	1 – 5	42	71,2
2.	6 – 10	14	23,7
3.	11 – 15	2	3,4
4.	≥ 16	1	1,7
Total		59	100,0

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed Data)

Table 1.4 based on years of employment shows that the most dominant respondents have been working for 1 to 5 years, amounting to 42 (71.19%). Based on the respondent's tenure above, it illustrates that employees working at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan has a relatively young experience, but productive at work. The data collected by the educational background can be seen in Table 1.5 below:

Table 1.5: Characteristics of Respondents by Education

No.	Education	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	Senior High School and its equivalent	22	37,3
2.	D-3	5	8,5
3.	S-1	32	54,2
Total		59	100,0

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed data).

Table 1.5 showed research results based on the educational background characteristics and indicate that the predominant proportion of respondent's education is on the level of Strata 1 (bachelor degree), which totaled 32 people (54.24%). Based on the education of the respondents above, it illustrates that employees who work at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan has higher educational background of Strata 1 (S-1). This suggests that it takes a higher education qualification to face competition in the automotive industry businesses that propagate more rapidly. The sampled results of the data collection based on the marital status of respondents can be seen in Table 1.6 below:

Table 1.6: Characteristics of Respondents by Marital Status

No.	Marital Status	Number (People)	Percentage (%)
1.	Married	37	62,7
2.	Single	22	37,3
Total		59	100,0

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed Data).

Based on Table 1.6, marital status characteristics indicate that the most dominant marital status of respondents is married that totaled 37 people (62.71%). Respondents' marital status above illustrates that employees working in PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan are mostly married so that employees are assumed to work seriously, considering it has a sense of responsibility for their families.

3.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Testing Hypothesis states that Recruitment (X1), Training (X2), Placement (X3) significantly affects employee performance (Y) at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. Result in Table 1.8 below shown based on the regression of primary data that have been processed.

Table 1.7: Results of Multiple Regressions

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.465	.644		2.273	.027
Employees' Recruitment	.138	.065	.246	2.114	.039
Employees' Training	.463	.119	.423	3.884	.000
Employees' Placement	.163	.080	.236	2.035	.047

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Findings, 2019 (processed data).

Table 1.7 is based on the multiple linear regression equation in this study and presented as follows:

$$Y = 1.465 + 0.138X_1 + 0.463X_2 + 0.163X_3$$

The regression model above obtained a constant value of 1.465 or positive and significant effect on the performance of employees. In the equation, it can be seen that Recruitment (X1), Training (X2) and Placement (X3) affect the increase or decrease in the dependent variable of employee performance (Y), all independent variables have positive regression coefficient of the performance of employees at PT. Astra International Tbk, AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan.

3.2 Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

Simultaneous Test (Test-F) were conducted to see whether there has been an influence from the independent variable (X_1, X_2, X_3), namely recruitment, training, placement on employee performance which is the dependent variable (Y). Simultaneous Test Results (Test - F) can be seen in Table 1.9 below:

Table 1.8: Simultaneous Test (Test – F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.600	3	.200	9.937	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.108	55	.020		
	Total	1.708	58			

a. Dependent Variable: performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), placement, training, recruitment

Source: Research Findings, 2019 (processed data)

From Table 1.8, the F_{count} value is 9.937 with a significance of 0.000 while the F_{table} value is at the 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.05$), then the F_{table} value is $0.05 (2.56) = 3.161$ so $F_{count} > F_{table}$ is $9.937 > 3.161$ so the decision is H_0 rejected H_a accepted, which means that the recruitment of the independent variable (X_1), Training (X_2), placement (X_3) show significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. Astra International, Tbk AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan.

3.3 Partial Testing of Hypotheses (t-Test)

T-test aims to see partially the influence of the independent variable, the variable Recruitment (X_1), Training (X_2) and Placement (X_3) to variable (Y) employee performance. Partial Test Results can be seen in Table 1.10 below:

Table 1.9: Partial Test Results (t-Test)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.465	.644		2.273	.027
	Employees' Recruitment	.138	.065	.246	2.114	.039
	Employees' Training	.463	.119	.423	3.884	.000
	Employees' Placement	.163	.080	.236	2.035	.047

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Findings, 2019 (processed data)

Based on Table 1.9, it can be seen that:

- 1) The influence of the Recruitment variable (X_1) on Performance (Y) partially has a significant value of 0.039. This means that it is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$, the value of t_{count} is obtained = 2.114 while t_{table} 2.002 means $t_{count} \geq t_{table}$ thus concluded H_0 is rejected, and vice versa H_1 states that there is a significant effect of recruitment on performance.

- 2) The influence of the Training variable (X2) on Performance (Y) partially has a significant value of 0.00. This means that it is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$, the value of t_{count} is obtained = 3.884 while t_{table} 2.002 means $t_{count} \geq t_{table}$ thus concluded H_0 is rejected, and vice versa H_1 states that there is a very significant effect of training on performance.
- 3) The influence of the Placement variable (X3) on Performance (Y) partially has a significant value of 0.00. This means that it is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$, the value of t_{count} is obtained = 2.035 while t_{table} 2.002 means $t_{count} \geq t_{table}$ thus concluded that H_0 is rejected, and vice versa H_1 states that there is a significant effect of placement on performance.

3.4 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The coefficient of determination test (R^2) is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2013). The smaller Adjusted R^2 value means the ability of the independent variable Recruitment (X1), Training (X2), and Placement (X3) to influence the dependent variable of Employee Performance (Y) at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. The coefficient of determination can be seen in Table 1.11 below:

Table 1.10: Determination Coefficient Test Results (R^2)

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.593 ^a	.352	.316	.14191	.717
a. Predictors: (Constant), placement, training, recruitment					
b. Dependent Variable: performance					

Source: Research Results, 2019 (Processed Data)

Based on Table 1.10, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0,316, or 31.6%. This declared variable employee performance (Y) is explained by variables Recruitment (X1), Training (X2), placement (X3). The remaining 68.4% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study such as the selection and discipline.

4. Discussion

4.1 Recruitment influence on employee performance

Based on the partial results of hypothesis testing, it can be seen that the variable Recruitment has a positive influence on the performance of employees at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM Raja Medan. Recruitment is an important issue for companies in the procurement of labor. By means of the planning decisions regarding the management of human resources such as the number of employees needed, the period of when it is needed, and what criteria is needed to define and attract applicants who have a good ability to work within a company or organization

According to Kaswan (2012: 66) recruitment is the practice or activity by the organization with the main purpose to identify and bind to potential employees who are qualified. Good and ideal recruitment is needed to improve the performance of employees in the organization, good and well-conducted recruitment will be able to produce human resources who have good performance, quality and competence to achieve organizational goals.

4.2 Effect of Training on Employee Performance

Based on the partial results of hypothesis testing, training variable is known to have a positive influence more dominantly to the performance of employees at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. This is in line with the views of Bangun (2012: 202), who mentioned that training is the process of improving skills of employees to help meet the goals of the company. Training is a vehicle for building human resources to the globalization era which is full of challenges. Training activities cannot be ignored, especially in terms of job skills development, health and safety for employees. Therefore, training must be a fundamental part that cannot be separated for the development of the organization or company as a whole.

4.3 Effect of Placement on Employee Performance

Based on the results of the partial hypothesis, it can be seen that placement variable has a positive influence on the performance of employees at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan. Placement of the right employees is a key to obtaining work performance optimum of each employee in addition to working capital, creativity and initiative. This is in line with the opinion of Sondra, S (2012: 123) who argued that the concept of placement include the sale, transfer, and demotion. This placement must be based on the job description and job specification that have been determined and are guided by the principle of *"placing the right people in the right place and placing the right person for the right position"* or *"the right man in the right place and the right man behind the right job."*

Based on the results of research and discussion that has been described previously, the conclusions that can be drawn are as follows:

- 1) Results obtained simultaneous hypothesis that recruitment, training and placement give positive and significant impact on the performance of employees at PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan.
- 2) Based on testing of the independent variables partially of the three independent variables (Recruitment, Training, Placement), the most dominant variables which affects to the performance of employees of PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan is no other than training program. It can be seen from the results of standardized coefficient, which indicates that the variable Training (X2) has the highest value.
- 3) Based on the result of determination (R²) of 0.316 which indicates that 31.6% variable employee performance (Y) can be explained by Recruitment (X1),

Training (X2) and Placement (X3). 68.4% is the influence of other factors that are not explained by this research model.

4.4 Suggestion

Based on the research conclusions, the researchers would like to provide some recommendations, namely:

- 1) PT. Astra International Tbk, Toyota AUTO 2000 SM. Raja Medan should pay attention and improve more on the aspect of job training. It is because job training has a significant influence on employee performance, and continuously makes better improvements. Job training should be held in order to work in line with the company's activities that include marketing car brands of Toyota, selling spare parts (original spare parts) for Toyota brand vehicles as well as service vehicles. These work activities in each part really require continuous and organized training to produce good performance so that the company's goals can be achieved.
- 2) For further research, it is expected to be examined by other variables outside the research variables in order to obtain more varied results that can describe any matters that may affect employee performance. The future study may also extend the period of research to expand its coverage and the use of different analytical methods.

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